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Abstract: Pollution associated to traffic can be considered one of the most relevant pollution sources in our cities; noise is one of the major components of traffic pollution; thus, efforts are necessary to search adequate noise assessment methods and low pollution city designs. Different methods have been proposed for the evaluation of noise in cities, including the categorization method, which is based on the functionality concept. Until now, this method has only been studied (with encouraging results) for short-term, diurnal measurements, but nocturnal noise presents a behavior clearly different on respect to the diurnal one. In this work 45 continuous measurements of approximately one week each in duration are statistically analyzed to identify differences between the proposed categories. The results show that the five proposed categories highlight the noise stratification of the studied city in each period of the day (day, evening, and night).

A comparison of the continuous measurements with previous short-term measurements indicates that the latter can be a good approximation of the former in diurnal period, reducing the resource expenditure for noise evaluation.

Annoyance estimated from the measured noise levels was compared with the response of population obtained from a questionnaire with good agreement.

The categorization method can yield good information about the distribution of a pollutant associated to traffic in our cities in each period of the day and, therefore, is a powerful tool for town planning and the design of pollution prevention policies.

Response to Reviewers: Answer to Reviewer #2:

1.- We agree with the reviewer that in a general noise study, noise measurement must be complemented with annoyance assessment. Thus, simultaneously to the analysis of sampling strategies for noise assessment, we have been working in the study of the response of population. In this line we developed some years ago a questionnaire to study this response (Barrigón Morillas JM, Vílchez Gómez R, Gómez Escobar V, Méndez Sierra JA, Tejeiro Vidal C, Alejandro Bueno L, Vaquero Martínez JM. Presentación de una encuesta para la realización de estudios sociales sobre el impacto del ruido urbano. Rev Española Acust 2002; 33:27-33). This questionnaire was used in the city of Cáceres as previously published (Barrigón Morillas JM, Gómez Escobar V, Méndez Sierra JA, Vílchez-Gómez R,

ANALYZING NOCTURNAL NOISE STRATIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

Pollution associated to traffic can be considered one of the most relevant pollution sources in our cities; noise is one of the major components of traffic pollution; thus, efforts are necessary to search adequate noise assessment methods and low pollution city designs. Different methods have been proposed for the evaluation of noise in cities, including the *categorization method*, which is based on the functionality concept. Until now, this method has only been studied (with encouraging results) for short-term, diurnal measurements, but nocturnal noise presents a behavior clearly different on respect to the diurnal one. In this work 45 continuous measurements of approximately one week each in duration are statistically analyzed to identify differences between the proposed categories. The results show that the five proposed categories highlight the noise stratification of the studied city in each period of the day (day, evening, and night).

A comparison of the continuous measurements with previous short-term measurements indicates that the latter can be a good approximation of the former in diurnal period, reducing the resource expenditure for noise evaluation.

Annoyance estimated from the measured noise levels was compared with the response of population obtained from a questionnaire with good agreement.

The *categorization method* can yield good information about the distribution of a pollutant associated to traffic in our cities in each period of the day and, therefore, is a powerful tool for town planning and the design of pollution prevention policies.

Keywords: urban pollution, noise sampling methods, urban planning, annoyance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Noise is one of the major urban pollutant, affecting the majority of the streets of modern cities, and it is present throughout almost all hours of the day (WHO, 1999). Thus, in the last decades, several noise studies have been conducted in different cities regarding different aspects of noise pollution, such as noise characteristics [sampling strategies (Barrigón Morillas, et al., 2005b; Romeu et al., 2011), uncertainty (Ausejo et al., 2011; Romeu et al., 2011, Torija and Ruiz, 2012; Barrigón and Prieto, 2014), sources (Zeng and Zhan, 2005; Yang et al., 2011), contamination levels (Arana, 2010; Ko et al., 2010), annoyance (Miedema and Oudshoorn, 2001; Kim et al., 2010; Paviotti and Vogiatzis, 2012), psychological effects of noise (Öhrström, 2004; Fyhri and Klæboe, 2009; Fyhri and Aasvang, 2010) and proposal of noise action plans (Naish, 2010; Vogiatzis and Remy, 2013). Road traffic is the primary origin of noise pollution and also of some other major city pollutants (Can et al., 2011b; Chen et al., 2008, Foraster et al., 2011; Su et al., 2008) which are the cause of different damaging effects on the citizens health and have influence also in the increase in house prices (Brandt and Maennig, 2011; Freitas et al., 2012; Lam and Chung, 2012).

In the analysis of the acoustic conditions of a given city or area, two different variables must be taken into consideration: spatial and temporal variation. Thus, sampling strategies can be classified according to these two variables.

Referring to the spatial variation, an adequate sampling strategy is dramatically important for noise mapping both for *in situ* measurements and for computational methods. Particularly, computational methods are recommended in different standards (ISO 1996-2, 2007) and legislations (COM, 2002). Nevertheless the recommended computation methods for road traffic noise need different kinds of *in situ* measurements: firstly, a wide traffic flow sampling through all the streets of the city in order to an adequate characterization of the sound source; secondly, noise measurements to calibrate the model and to check the precision of the estimated noise values (WG-AEN, 2007).

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4 Therefore, it should be of great interest the development of a low cost method that could allow
5 obtaining highly predictive results for *in situ* noise measurements. And, in addition, this method
6 could allow an easy and efficient acquisition of traffic flows, and provide noise values for testing
7 the accuracy of computational results. In example, Ausejo found an important decrease in the
8 uncertainty of a computation noise model when the sampling strategy is improved and *in situ*
9 measurements are carried out (Ausejo et al., 2011).
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17 Based on the concept of functionality, a recently proposed group of category definitions has
18 shown that it is possible to stratify the intensity of noise pollution in city streets: the
19 *categorization method*. In previous studies, it was shown that these categories can highlight the
20 stratification of urban noise (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005b) and, recently, its applicability has
21 been studied in urban centers ranging in size from 2,000 inhabitants to 700,000 (Rey Gozalo et
22 al., 2013). The results show that, for even a fairly small number of measurements, the various
23 strata (categories) are statistically significantly different. Thus, it was possible to precisely
24 estimate noise levels in the unsampled streets. Consequently, the basis of the method and even
25 the definition of categories could also be applied in such fields as urban planning or noise
26 pollution control. Moreover, because traffic is also a source of other important pollutants, this
27 method might extendable to such pollutants. Previous studies show the relationships between
28 street noise and ambient air quality and their combined impacts on the surrounding environment
29 (Kim et al., 2012) and how land use distribution determine the location of emission sources and
30 the pattern of urban traffic, affecting urban air quality (Borrego et al., 2006).
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45 Referring to the temporal variation, as also is indicated in the European Directive 2002/49/CE
46 (COM, 2002) and some international standards (ISO 1996-2, 2007), noise indicators must be
47 determined over a period of a year. This assessment can be easily performed using modern
48 acoustical instrumentation, but noise-monitoring stations are quite expensive and can only be
49 used at very specific locations. Thus, as an alternative, the most extended temporal strategy is
50 recording measurements for less than a year and extrapolating them to obtain a year of data.
51 The duration of these measurements can vary widely, from minutes to hours (Doygun and
52 Gurun, 2008; Zannin et al. 2011; Romeu et al., 2011) to a whole day (Banerjee et al, 2008;
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4 Onnu, 2000; Van Renterghem et al., 2012). Longer periods of time are rarely used (Alberola et
5 al, 2005, Can et al., 2011a; Mioduszewski et al., 2011). Unfortunately, methods to assess the
6 real day-evening-night sound level $L_{A_{den}}$ from short-term measurements with the required
7 precision have not yet been developed (Wolde, 2003). Thus, the extrapolation of these
8 measurements to the year period can produce significant inaccuracies if the measurement
9 period is not representative of the year period, as in the case of singular noise events (Prieto
10 Gajardo et al., 2011). When the data used for the extrapolation are not representative of the
11 entire year, errors of > 2 dBA can be produced (Bambrilla, 2001). We must consider that short-
12 term measurements are usually carried out during the daytime, which generally has less
13 variability than other periods of the day, such as nighttime.
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25 Previously, the categorization method has only been applied to short-term diurnal
26 measurements (thereby only yielding information about the day sound level L_{Ad}), focusing on
27 showing that this method allows the identification of the noise stratification present in cities and
28 villages (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005b; Rey Gozalo et al., 2013). Despite the large number of
29 cities and villages analyzed and the good results obtained, previous studies have not tested the
30 validity of the method for continuous measurements or for other sound indicators commonly
31 used in noise assessment, such as the evening sound level L_{Ae} , the night sound level L_{An} , and
32 the day-evening-night sound level $L_{A_{den}}$.
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42 The extension of the applicability of the categorization method to continuous measurements first
43 requires proving that previous results obtained with short-term measurements are not
44 statistically distinguishable from those obtained with continuous measurements in the same time
45 period. Moreover, this confirmation does not guarantee the validity of the *categorization method*
46 for unstudied periods of the day, such as the evening or night. The city of Cáceres (Spain) has
47 been the site of a considerably high number of continuous measurements (of approximately one
48 week each) and is used in this study to allow a deeper analysis of the applicability of the
49 categorization method to continuous measurements. Moreover, this city has previously been
50 studied in great detail using short-term measurements.
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4 Nocturnal noise levels presents a behavior clearly different if compared with the diurnal one,
5 both in temporal structure and in average values (Mioduszewski et al., 2011). Although there
6 are some studies that relate diurnal noise levels with long-term indicators (which include the
7 nocturnal period) (Schultz, 1978; Rey Gozalo et al., 2012), until now there are practically no jobs
8 in which the stratification of nocturnal noise were proved. Previous studies nocturnal noise
9 levels are estimated from its relationship with the whole day noise level (Jimenez et al, 2008),
10 but the proposed categories presented significant differentiation problems. In addition to
11 analyzing the stratification of the nocturnal noise values in the present work, it is examined
12 whether these layers are the same as those proposed in previous works where, for diurnal
13 period, significantly differences among them were observed. Therefore, the main objective of
14 the present study is the evaluation of the application of the method to some sonorous
15 categorization indicators (L_{Ad} , L_{Ae} , L_{An} , and L_{Ade}) obtained from continuous measurements.
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28 Moreover, previous studies of Romeu, (Romeu et al., 2011) show the error in the estimation of
29 day levels using short-term measurements in a classification of city streets in three groups:
30 urban ring roads, main streets and ordinary streets. In the present work, we proposed five
31 different categories and multiple comparison tests are carried out, in order to solve the different
32 hypotheses. This kind of tests did not find significant differences in mean values of the
33 categories proposed by Romeu (Jimenez et al., 2008). Thus, a secondary objective of the study
34 is the evaluation of the possible differences in the application of this method to short-term and
35 continuous measurements.
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45 Finally, another secondary objective of the study is to analyze the ability of the categorization
46 method to calculate the noise annoyance. To this effect, some mathematical equations have
47 been proposed for determine annoyance due to traffic noise (Miedema and Vos, 1998;
48 Miedema and Oudshoorn, 2001; Miedema et al., 2003); some of these equations are the basis
49 of international standards or reports (ISO 1996-1, 2003; WHO, 2009), although some authors
50 have found that these expressions cannot be totally appropriate in case of the existence of a
51 high presence of noise traffic sources such as mopeds, scooters and motorbikes (Paviotti and
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4 Vogiatzis, 2012). These annoyance estimations were compared with the results of some of the
5 questions of a sociological study carried out in the studied city (Barrigón Morillas et al, 2005a).
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10 Section 2 describes the method and the city where the measurements were carried out. Section
11 3 presents and discusses the results. Finally, Section 4 presents the most relevant conclusions.
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14 15 **2. METHODS**

16 17 18 19 **2.1. City studied**

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21 The present work was carried out in the city of Cáceres, the second largest town in
22 Extremadura (a region in southwestern Spain). It has a population of approximately 95 000
23 inhabitants (increasing to over 110 000 during the teaching period due to the influx of over
24 10 000 students at the University of Extremadura and a large number of tourists). In recent
25 years, the construction of a ring-road around the town has changed its traffic patterns, greatly
26 reducing the number of heavy vehicles and, to a lesser extent, other vehicles that pass through
27 the town. Industrial activities are of minor relevance and are concentrated mainly in the
28 outskirts. The mean annual temperature and rainfall are 16.1°C and 523 mm, respectively.
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38 **2.2. Sampling method**

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40 As previously mentioned, the categorization method was used in this study. The category
41 definitions were the same described in previous works (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005b, 2010;
42 Rey Gozalo et al., 2013):
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- 45 • *Type 1* includes those preferred streets whose function is to form connections with
46 other Spanish towns and to interconnect those preferred streets. In general, these
47 streets are indicated by a system of road signs.
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- 50 • *Type 2* includes those streets that provide access to the major distribution nodes of the
51 town. For the purpose of this study, a distribution node is considered to exist when at
52 least four major streets meet. This definition does not include any possible nodes of
53 preferred streets as defined in Type 1, above. This category also includes streets
54 normally used as alternatives to Type 1 streets in the case of traffic saturation.
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- *Type 3* includes streets that lead to regional roads, streets that provide access from those streets of Types 1 and 2 to centers of interest in the town (hospitals, shopping malls, etc.), and streets that clearly allow communication between streets of Types 1 and 2.
 - *Type 4* includes all other streets that clearly allow communication between the three previously defined types of street, as well as the principal streets of the different districts of the town that were not included in the previously defined categories.
 - *Type 5* comprises the rest of the streets of the town except pedestrian-only streets.
 - *Type 6* comprises all the pedestrian-only streets.

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As the assumption behind this method of street categorization is that traffic is the most important source of noise pollution, the sixth category was not included in the present study. In any case, pedestrian-only streets usually represent a very small percentage of all the streets in a city.

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Once assigned the town's streets to these categories, several sampling points were required for each category. For the selection of these sampling points, different balconies were chosen, taking into consideration the category of the street, the access availability, their protection against vandalism and the non-equivalence with other balconies (equivalent balconies were those located on the same section of a street with no important intersection between them).

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In Figure 1, the categorization of the different streets of the city and the locations of the sampling points are presented. A total number of 45 sampling points were used: 8 in Category 1, 8 in Category 2, 6 in Category 3, 8 in Category 4, and 15 in Category 5.

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All measurements were performed following the ISO 1996-2 guidelines (ISO 1996-2, 1987, 2007) using 2236, 2238 or 2260 Brüel & Kjaer type I sound level meters. Each measurement lasted approximately one week, with data recorded every minute. A weighting was used in all measurements.

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4 The monitoring stations were composed of a metallic box (to protect the sound level meter and
5 the external battery), a 2-m spoke (to avoid the effect of the reflection of sound waves by the
6 back wall), and an outdoor microphone kit (Brüel & Kjaer UA-1404) (to protect the microphone
7 from adverse weather conditions). When possible, the monitoring stations were placed in
8 different balconies or terraces located a height of 4 m (COM, 2002). Values obtained in
9 balconies with a height higher than 4 m where were normalized to a height of 4 m as proposed
10 in the "Guide du Bruit des Transports Terrestrial. Prévision sonores des niveaux" (CETUR,
11 1980) for streets with a U-shaped longitudinal profile and as described in the ISO 9613-2
12 standard (ISO 9613-2, 1996) for streets with an L-shaped longitudinal profile.
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23 For the analysis for the secondary study objective, the comparison of continuous and short-
24 term measurements, the short-term measurements used were those from a previous study of
25 the city of Cáceres (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2011). These measurements were carried out on
26 different days of the week (only workdays were studied) and during different periods of the day
27 (at each sampling point, three measurements were distributed along the diurnal period). The
28 sampling time for each measurement was 15 min. These short-term measurements were
29 carried out in 2005 following the ISO 1996-2 guidelines (ISO 1996-2, 2007) using a 2238 Brüel
30 & Kjaer type I sound level meter, with tripod and windshield, located 1 m from the curb and
31 placed at a height of 1.5 m. Calibration was performed using a 4231 Brüel & Kjaer calibrator.
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42 **2.3. Calculation of the population annoyed by noise**

43 To calculate the population annoyed by traffic noise two different methods were employed.
44 Firstly, it was estimated as per some equations proposed by other authors and internationally
45 validated. Thus, the percentages of annoyed (%A) and highly annoyed (%HA) population were
46 estimated from $L_{A_{den}}$ indicator with the following equations (Miedema and Oudshoorn, 2001;
47 ISO 1996-1, 2003):
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$$53 \quad \%A = 0.0001795 (L_{A_{den}} - 37)^3 + 0.0211 (L_{A_{den}} - 37)^2 + 0.5353 (L_{A_{den}} - 37) \quad (1)$$

$$54 \quad \%HA = 0.0009868 (L_{A_{den}} - 42)^3 - 0.01436 (L_{A_{den}} - 42)^2 + 0.5118 (L_{A_{den}} - 42) \quad (2)$$

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4 Referring only to nocturnal noise, the percentages of citizens lowly sleep disturbed (%LSD),
5 sleep disturbed (%SD) and highly sleep disturbed (%HSD) were estimated from the L_{An}
6 indicator with the following equations (Miedema et al., 2003):
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$$\%LSD = (- 8.4) + 0.16 L_{An} + 0.01081 (L_{An})^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\%SD = 13.8 - 0.85 L_{An} + 0.01670 (L_{An})^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\%HSD = 20.8 - 1.05 L_{An} + 0.01486 (L_{An})^2 \quad (5)$$

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19 Secondly, for the purpose of comparing the estimated annoyance with the response of
20 population, results of a parallel sociological study were considered (only the answers
21 corresponding to the questions referred to annoyance due to traffic and to alteration of sleep
22 due to noise). A total of 390 subjects were randomly selected according to their residence
23 following the categorization method. Consequently, the results can be classified according to
24 the category of the street of the resident. The procedure was door-to-door, with the interviewer
25 present. More information about the questionnaire and the survey can be found in previous
26 works (Barrigón Morillas et al, 2002; 2005a).
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38 **2.4. Statistical analyses**

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40 The continuous equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq}) was chosen for the different statistical tests used
41 to analyze the results and evaluate the quality of the category classification because L_{Aeq} is
42 most commonly used in noise studies. Nevertheless, the sampling point locations are not
43 similar and obtained values must to be normalized. Thus, to normalize these distances, for
44 each measured L_{Aeq} , the sound power level by length unit (L_{Aw}) was calculated to allow a
45 comparison. For corrections, the methods described in some ISO standards were considered
46 (ISO 1996-2, 2007; ISO 9613-2, 1996). One order of reflection was considered; reflections on
47 front of building were treated with the help of image sources, as used in several national
48 calculation methods (EC, 2003).
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59 After calculating the different sound power levels, the hypotheses of the statistical analyses
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- 7 • Null hypothesis (H_0): There are no significant differences between the L_{wx} values (dBA)
8 of the different categories.
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- 10 • Alternative hypothesis (H_1): There are significant differences between the L_{wx} values
11 (dBA) of the different categories.
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17 where x is the time period of the sound indicator considered: e.g., 7:00 to 19:00 for L_{Ad} , 19:00 to
18 23:00 for L_{Ae} , and 23:00 to 7:00 for L_{An} .
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23 To address the previous hypotheses at a probability of at least 95%, that is, with a degree of
24 significance (α) equal to 0.05, the nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney U-tests
25 were used (Mann and Whitney, 1947; Kruskal and Wallis, 1952; Holm, 1979). These
26 nonparametric tests were used due to the small number of samples, which makes a normal
27 distribution unlikely.
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34 The Kruskal-Wallis test (Kruskal and Wallis, 1952) was used to compare the five categories to
35 identify any significant differences. When such differences were found, as they were in all cities,
36 as shown below, Mann-Whitney U-tests were used to compare pairs of categories. The Mann-
37 Whitney U-test is a nonparametric test for assessing whether two independent samples or
38 observations come from the same distribution. This test was used to compare pairs of separate
39 categories within the same population. To avoid any errors due to the use of data from the same
40 population rather than randomly selected data, the Holm correction was used (Holm, 1979).
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50 In contrast to the previous statistical tests, we used the receiver operating characteristics (ROC)
51 analysis to study the predictive capacity and other characteristics that refer to the classification
52 capacity of this method (Hand and Till, 2001; Fawcett, 2006, Torija and Ruiz, 2012). ROC
53 analysis allows us to calculate the sensibility (capacity to include previously assigned streets in
54 the stratum), non-specificity (proportion of streets that were not initially assigned to a certain
55 stratum but that the ROC analysis indicated belonged to that stratum), and predictive values
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(proportion of the streets that the ROC analysis assigned to a stratum that matched the categories to which they were initially assigned, relative to the total number of streets that the ROC analysis determined for the stratum) using the following equations:

$$\text{sensitivity} = \frac{\text{number of data classified correctly in category } i}{\text{number of data of the category } i} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{non - specificity} = \frac{\text{number of data classified incorrectly in category } i}{\text{number of data that no belongs to category } i} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{predictive value} = \frac{\text{number of data classified correctly in category } i}{\text{number of data that the ROC method includes in the category } i} \quad (8)$$

Finally, for the comparison between short-term and continuous measurements, the Mann-Whitney U-test was used to assess whether the two groups of measurements come from the same distribution.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Analysis of mean sound levels.

In Table I, the mean values of the different sonorous indicators are shown: L_{Ad} , L_{Ae} , L_{An} , and $L_{A\text{den}}$. In all the sub-day periods studied [day (from 7 a.m to 7 p.m) (L_{Ad}), evening (from 7 p.m. to 11 p.m.) (L_{Ae}), and night (from 11 p.m. to 7 a.m.) (L_{An}) and over the whole day ($L_{A\text{den}}$)]. There is a clear tendency of noise levels to decrease as the category number increases, on both workdays and non-workdays, as well as considering all the measured days (global). For a more adequate comparison, from the different sonorous indicators, for the global period, the sound power levels were calculated according to the previously mentioned normalization. These global sound power levels (also shown in Table I) were used to evaluate the statistical hypothesis.

First, the Kruskal-Wallis test was used, indicating significant differences ($p \leq 0.001$) for all the sonorous indicators studied (Table II). Thus, the Mann-Whitney U-test with Holm correction was

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4 then applied to analyze the differences among category pairs (Table III). As shown in Table III,
5 the Mann-Whitney U-test found significant differences ($p \leq 0.01$) among all pairs of categories
6 studied for all sound indicators analyzed (except categories 1-2 in the evening period, where
7 differences were significant with $p \leq 0.05$). This finding indicates that the stratification of noise
8 levels observed in previous short-term diurnal measurements studies is also found for
9 continuous measurements and is equally present in the evening and night periods. In all the
10 studied temporal periods, the five categories defined in the categorization method highlight this
11 stratification. Thus, the categorization method is a very powerful method for noise assessment,
12 allowing the noise values of cities to be characterized using a reduced number of sampling
13 points.
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25 Finally, to corroborate the quality of the previous results and to obtain more information about
26 the categorization method, the classification capacity of this method was studied via ROC
27 analysis. The results of this analysis are shown in Figure 2. From the results shown in this
28 table, we can note the following:
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- 32 - Regarding the ROC sensitivity (%), which is a measure of the capacity to include
33 previously assigned streets in the strata, all the categories have values at or above 87,
34 75, 93 and 100% for L_{Awd} , L_{Awe} , L_{Awn} , and L_{Awden} , respectively.
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- 37 - Regarding the non-specificity (%), which measures the proportion of streets that were
38 not initially assigned to a given stratum but that the ROC analysis indicates belong to
39 that stratum, all the obtained values were below 2.8%.
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- 42 - Finally, the predictive values of the different strata (which represent the proportion of
43 the streets that the ROC analysis assigned to the stratum that matched the categories
44 to which they were initially assigned, relative to the total number of streets that the
45 ROC analysis determined for the stratum) are very good: at or above 86, 78, 89, and
46 100% for L_{Awd} , L_{Awe} , L_{Awn} , and L_{Awden} , respectively.
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55 Therefore, we see that in each of the three periods analyzed and in the overall indicator (L_{Aden}),
56 the results showed a high predictive capacity. For the overall indicator the prediction capacity
57 was 100% in all categories. For the different period indicators, the worst result was in the
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4 evening period (almost 80%) and the best in the night (almost 90%). In this respect, it should
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6 be noted that night period is the most difficult interval to be evaluated with short-term
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8 measurements because of its variability.
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11 Thus, based on this high prediction capacity, this procedure seems to be very suitable for
12
13 further applications, such as noise prediction and the design of environmental policy.
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15 16 17 **3.2. Comparison of short-term and continuous measurements.** 18

19 As mentioned previously, previous studies of the categorization method used short-
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21 measurements in several villages or towns. It is therefore of great interest to analyze whether
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23 the results of this study from continuous measurement are similar to those obtained from short-
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25 term measurements. To this end, the results of this study were compared with the results
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27 obtained from short-term measurements carried for a methodology comparison study (Barrigón
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29 Morillas et al., 2011). For the present comparison, the values obtained from the short-term
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31 measurements were compared with the L_{Ad} values obtained from the continuous
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33 measurements after correcting these latter values to correspond to the location of the sound
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35 level meters used in the short-term measurements (1 m from the curb and a height of 1.5 m, as
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37 indicated previously).
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40 In Table IV, the mean values of L_{Ad} obtained from the short-term and continuous measurements
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42 are presented. The results from continuous measurements are different from those presented
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44 in Table I due to the aforementioned correction. As observed, the standard deviation is lower
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46 for the continuous measurements, as could be expected. For each category, the results from
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48 both groups (short-term and continuous measurements) were compared using the Mann-
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50 Whitney U-test with the Holm correction. The p-values obtained using this test were 0.460,
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52 0.696, 0.492, 0.203, and 0.807 for the groups of categories 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively. In all
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54 cases, these p-values correspond to non-significant differences ($p > 0.05$) among the two
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56 groups compared. These results indicate that the results obtained in the previous studies are
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58 good and that sampling procedures based on short-term measurements can give good
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60 approximations of the sound levels obtained in continuous measurements for diurnal period.
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3.3. Analysis and comparison of the proportions of the population annoyed by noise

As mentioned previously, proportions of population annoyed by traffic noise were calculated from the measured sound levels (from $L_{A_{den}}$ y L_{A_n} indicators); besides, the response of population was determined from the answers to the questionnaires. In Figure 3, the response of population for each category is shown join together with the lines corresponding to the previous equations for annoyance estimation [equations (1) to (5)]. As it can be seen, there is a common tendency in the response of population determined from the answers to the questionnaires and the annoyance predicted by the equations. Nevertheless in some cases, mainly in nocturnal period, there are some differences. Differences between response of population of each category and the estimated values are shown in Table V.

From these results we can conclude:

- There is a great similarity between %A and %HA predicted values and the obtained from the questionnaires (Figure 3A).
- Considering the values obtained for %A and %HA and the citizens living in each category (shown in Table V), values obtained for annoyance, although important, are lower than those obtained in other studies concerning other European cities (Martín et al., 2006; Paviotti and Vogiatzis, 2012).
- Values obtained for %LSD, %SD and %HSD indicator obtained from the questionnaires are generally lower than estimated.
- The L_{A_n} values higher than 40 dB in all the measured categories effect over sleep quality, well-being, environmental insomnia, complains... (WHO, 2009). Besides, in categories 1 to 4 (with near 34% of the city population) the L_{A_n} value higher than 50 dB implies possible effects on hypertension or myocardial infarction and, finally, in Category 1 ($L_{A_n}>60$ dB), psychic disorders (WHO, 2009).

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4 **4. CONCLUSIONS**
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7 It has been shown that there is a stratification of nocturnal noise levels, similar to this
8 previously demonstrated for diurnal ones. The proposed categories enable to estimate this
9 stratification.
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15 The present study also shows that the categorization method is an adequate tool for noise
16 assessment for all periods of the day, thus enabling the stratification of noise present in cities to
17 be identified. Therefore, with a reduced number of sampling points, a quick characterization of
18 the noise levels of cities can be achieved. Besides, a high degree of consistency was found
19 between annoyance estimated from measured noise levels and the response of population.
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27 A study of the sound level evolution during the sampling time and the results obtained from the
28 continuous measurements carried out also lead to the following additional conclusions:
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31 - The mean values of the analyzed sound indicators (L_{Ad} , L_{Ae} , L_{An} , and $L_{A\text{den}}$) decrease
32 as the number of the category increases. To create an adequate comparison, the
33 sound power levels were calculated from these indicators. A comparison of sound
34 power levels using the Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney U tests shows that the
35 differences among values of categories are statistically significant for a confidence
36 interval of 99%. This finding demonstrates the applicability of the categorization method
37 to continuous measurements, as can be applied to all periods of the day.
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45 - When analyzing the predictive values of different categories using ROC analysis, all
46 the categories presented values above 78%, indicating a good predictive capacity for
47 non-measured values. A 100% predictive capacity in all categories was obtained for
48 the $L_{A\text{wden}}$ indicator, and predictive capacities of 90% or higher were obtained for the
49 night indicator ($L_{A\text{wn}}$).
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56 - The comparison of the results obtained in this study to short-term measurement results
57 reveals no statistically significant differences between the groups of measurements for
58 the period compared (daytime). Thus, the urban stratification of noise evidenced in
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4 previous studies using the categorization method and short-term measurements has
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6 been validated by continuous measurements. This finding suggests that the results
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8 obtained from short-term measurements may be a good approximation, if the
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10 measurements are designed properly, to continuous measurements.

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12 - The results of this work seem to indicate that the concept of functionality (the basis of
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14 the categorization method) enable us to obtain good information about the distribution
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16 of noise levels in our cities for all periods of the day, estimated annoyance due to noise
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18 and can therefore be a good tool for town planning and the design of pollution
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20 prevention policies for noise as well as other traffic-related pollutants.
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TABLE I. Average values and standard deviation of L_{Aeq} and L_{Aw} values of the different studied sonorous indicators. The results are shown separately for working and festive days and for each category.

Category	Indicator	$\overline{L_{Aeqx}} \pm \sigma$		$\overline{L_{Awx}} \pm \sigma$	
		Workdays	Non-workdays	Global	Global
1	L_{Ad}/L_{Awd}	68.8±1.3	66.1±2.2	68.1±1.3	83.7±1.1
	L_{Ae}/L_{Awe}	68.0±1.9	66.9±1.9	67.6±1.9	83.2±1.4
	L_{Ar}/L_{Awn}	61.2±2.3	63.2±2.4	62.1±2.2	77.6±1.6
	L_{Ader}/L_{Awden}	70.7±1.4	70.6±2.2	70.8±1.6	86.3±1.1
2	L_{Ad}/L_{Awd}	66.8±1.9	65.2±2.9	66.5±2.1	81.5±1.7
	L_{Ae}/L_{Awe}	65.8±1.9	64.8±2.4	65.7±2.0	80.6±1.6
	L_{Ar}/L_{Awn}	58.6±2.3	59.0±2.3	58.9±2.0	73.9±1.4
	L_{Ader}/L_{Awden}	68.4±1.9	67.9±2.2	68.4±2.0	83.3±1.5
3	L_{Ad}/L_{Awd}	61.5±3.3	58.7±3.2	60.7±3.4	75.3±1.4
	L_{Ae}/L_{Awe}	61.3±3.2	60.2±2.8	60.9±3.1	75.6±1.2
	L_{Ar}/L_{Awn}	52.8±3.4	55.1±2.8	53.7±3.2	68.4±1.0
	L_{Ader}/L_{Awden}	63.1±3.3	63.0±2.8	63.1±3.2	77.8±1.1
4	L_{Ad}/L_{Awd}	60.5±2.2	57.6±2.1	59.6±2.1	72.3±0.6
	L_{Ae}/L_{Awe}	59.9±2.2	58.9±1.7	59.5±1.9	72.2±0.4
	L_{Ar}/L_{Awn}	51.8±1.8	54.1±1.9	52.8±1.8	65.5±1.1
	L_{Ader}/L_{Awden}	62.0±2.0	61.9±1.8	62.0±1.8	74.6±0.7
5	L_{Ad}/L_{Awd}	56.4±2.9	54.1±3.3	55.9±3.1	68.4±4.2
	L_{Ae}/L_{Awe}	56.0±3.8	54.9±3.6	55.7±3.7	68.2±4.5
	L_{Ar}/L_{Awn}	47.6±3.1	49.6±3.0	48.4±2.9	60.8±3.5
	L_{Ader}/L_{Awden}	58.2±2.8	58.0±2.9	58.1±2.8	70.6±3.7

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TABLE II. Results of the Kruskal-Wallis test applied to the different sonorous indicators. (*), (**), and (***) indicate the grade of significance of the differences ($p \leq 0.05$, $p \leq 0.01$, and $p \leq 0.001$, respectively). (n.s.) indicates a non-significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

Indicator	<i>P-value</i>
<i>L_{Awd}</i>	2.7E-08 (***)
<i>L_{Awe}</i>	2.9E-08 (***)
<i>L_{Awn}</i>	2.3E-08 (***)
<i>L_{Awden}</i>	2.1E-08 (***)

TABLE III. Results of the Mann-Whitney U-test applied to pairs of categories. (*), (**), and (***) indicate the level of significance of the differences ($p \leq 0.05$, $p \leq 0.01$, and $p \leq 0.001$, respectively). (n.s.) indicates a non-significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

	Category	1	2	3	4
L_{Awd}	2	4.7E-03 (**)	-	-	-
	3	2.7E-03 (**)	2.7E-03 (**)	-	-
	4	9.3E-04 (***)	9.3E-04 (***)	2.7E-03 (**)	-
	5	4.1E-05 (***)	4.1E-05 (***)	2.6E-04 (***)	4.1E-05 (***)
	Category	1	2	3	4
L_{Awe}	2	1.5E-02 (*)	-	-	-
	3	2.7E-03 (**)	2.7E-03 (**)	-	-
	4	9.3E-04 (***)	9.3E-04 (***)	2.7E-03 (**)	-
	5	4.1E-05 (***)	4.1E-05 (***)	2.6E-04 (***)	4.1E-05 (***)
	Category	1	2	3	4
L_{Awn}	2	9.3E-04 (***)	-	-	-
	3	2.0E-03 (**)	2.0E-03 (**)	-	-
	4	9.3E-04 (***)	9.3E-04 (***)	2.0E-03 (**)	-
	5	4.1E-05 (***)	4.1E-05 (***)	2.6E-04 (***)	1.3E-04 (***)
	Category	1	2	3	4
L_{Awden}	2	9.3E-04 (***)	-	-	-
	3	2.0E-03 (**)	2.0E-03 (**)	-	-
	4	9.3E-04 (***)	9.3E-04 (***)	2.0E-03 (**)	-
	5	4.1E-05 (***)	4.1E-05 (***)	2.6E-04 (***)	4.1E-05 (***)

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TABLE IV. Category mean values obtained from short-term and continuous measurements.

Category	Short-term L_{Ad}	Continuous L_{Ad}
1	73.6±2.7	72.9±1.9
2	70.9±2.4	69.8±2.0
3	68.2±3.1	66.7±1.4
4	65.8±2.9	64.8±0.8
5	59.8±5.1	60.4±3.6

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TABLE V. Observed differences between the response of population determined from the answers to the questionnaires (X_e) and the estimated values from the proposed equations (X_r) (Miedema and Oudshoorn, 2001; Miedema et al., 2003). Percentage of citizens of each category is also shown.

Category	% Citizens	Error (%A _r -%A _e)	Error (%HA _r -%HA _e)	Error (%LSD _r -%LSD _e)	Error (%SD _r -%SD _e)	Error (%HSD _r -%HSD _e)
1	4.8	2.4	1.3	-3.8	8.6	-5.6
2	6.2	-3.5	-1.7	-11.9	1.7	-3.8
3	7.2	1.5	8.3	2.6	8.3	-1.3
4	15.0	-13.2	12.0	-3.2	4.2	-3.3
5	66.9	-0.9	1.0	8.2	0.8	-0.7

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Street categorization of the city of Cáceres and location of the sampling points.

Figure 2. Results of ROC analysis for the different sonorous indicators

Figure 3. Percentages annoyance indicators obtained from the proposed equations (Miedema and Oudshoorn, 2001; Miedema et al., 2003) and from the answers to the questionnaires (*). A) Percentages of annoyed (%A) and highly annoyed (%HA) population; B) Percentages of lowly sleep disturbed (%LSD), sleep disturbed (%SD) and highly sleep disturbed (%HSD) population.

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Figure 1

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Figure 3